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INNOVATIVE FUNCTIONAL CURRICULUM AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN THE PERIOD OF COVID-19: THE NIGERIAN EXPERIENCE

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ABSTRACT

The paper tries to point out the phase of innovative curriculum in this era of covid-19 pandemic to be able to achieve the 2030 sustainable development goal agenda, most especially in Nigeria. It is no more news that the covid-19 pandemic forces a new paradigm on us as a nation, and all we have to do is to respond swiftly through nations curriculum, since it has been established that education is central to achieving all other sustainable development goals (SDGs), delivering education in a manner that is different from what we are used to as a nation. The paper therefore, stresses the need to have an innovative functional curriculum for our education delivery. This is the only way to ensure that the covid-19 pandemic did not stand as a barrier to achieving the United Nations Sustainable development goals. The paper recommends that there should be a sharp shift from the conventional educational delivery to the 21st century delivery, if we are to record any meaningful success towards achieving the 2030 agenda of the sustainable development goals (SDGs).

Keywords: Education, Curriculum, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Covid-19, Innovation

Introduction

Education is central to our existence as human, and it is because of these reason that education is perceived in different forms such as formal, informal and semi-formal. So, to pin education to a particular definition has been a bit difficult, this is because scholars have tried to come up with different definition based on their ideas of what they perceived education to be. But in whatever form it comes, it would be observed that education is central to human existence. This is why different cultures and different societies perceived education in different ways in terms of what education really is and what it aspires to achieve.

Scholars and authors have defined education in terms of their cultural peculiarities and experience, it is for this reason that the concept of education has not lent itself to a particular definition on any strict consensual definition as it depends on perspectives from which it is been viewed by the scholar defining the concept.

Encyclopedia Britanica defines education as the transmission of values and accumulated knowledge of a society. To Akinpelu (1984), he defined education as

an enabling agency by which the African could restore their self-confidence, and make those who doubted the humanity of Africans begins to revise their views and learn to respect Africans. While Adeyinka (1985) describes education as the process of transmitting the culture of a society from one generation to the other. However, Adesina (1985) sees education has been always related to variables such as purpose of learner, the aim of the teacher, as well as the technological problems of the society, so, it will be difficult to pin the concept of education down to a particular definition as; The tool for the integration of the individual effectively into a society so that the individual can achieve self-realisation, develop national consciousness, promote unity and strive for social, economic, political, scientific, cultural and technological process.

Therefore, since education is a process of cultural transmission, it means that for any meaningful education to take place, there must be something to indicate its contents and procedures which is what is referred to as the curriculum. This is because, the curriculum has a significant factor in the process of impacting knowledge. It is therefore not possible to have a meaningful education without a curriculum, which is the framework that determines what happens in the process of education. It was for this reason that Kolawole (2012), describes education and curriculum as a 'Siamese Twins'.

The Concept of a Curriculum

Curriculum experts have tried for decades to define curriculum with different opinion just like the concept of education. Some came up with definitions that they believe explains the concepts, while others came up with criticism. However, it must be noted that the controversy in defining curriculum is what has led to different definitions by curriculum scholars based on different philosophical positions.

Dada, Kolawole and Arikpo (2012), defines curriculum as the 'what' and 'how' of any educational enterprise. 'What' is the content or body of knowledge and 'how' is the procedure or methodology to be adopted. While to Nichols (2012), curriculum is what happens to student for which the school is responsible. It is the sum total of human endeavor geared towards the realization of the aspiration of the society through the institution of school. The major variables in human endeavor are the teachers (who implement the curriculum); the students (who are basically learners that the curriculum is planned for); the support system (from government and private initiatives); and the curriculum planners (who are usually experts that design the curriculum, recommend implementation strategies and evaluate to ascertain the extent of achievability of curriculum objectives). It can be said that a curriculum is a programme of studies, a programme of activities, a programme of guidance, and a proposed document stating intentions, time frame for implementation and evaluation.

Schools are social institutions established by the society and assigned the responsibility for teaching those aspects of the culture that have been formally selected and organized for transmission to future generations. And to be able to do this effectively, the school should design and use the curriculum, which is expected to help transform the society through education. The curriculum is the means through which education is transacted. Without a curriculum, education has no vehicle, nothing through which to transmit its messages, and values (Tailor and Richard, 1979:11 cited in Onyemerekeya. The curriculum therefore, is at the heart of an educational enterprise, and it is used as an instrument to implement society's educational goals. The curriculum however, to be relevant must solve the learners' problem as well as societal problem and that is why it must be constantly reviewed to reflect the emergent need of the society.

Curriculum Innovation

Innovation involves the introduction of something new in curriculum that deviates from the standard practice, which means adopting different methods and designs for learning to make learning more meaningful and responsive to solving emergent societal problems, because of the dynamic nature of our society, however it is done, innovation occur often because the society is changing, and to be able to address these changes through education using the curriculum, innovations are created. To make innovation effective therefore, it must be related to the educational objectives of the society and must reflect the needs, interest, values and problems, of the society as well as the learners found in such society. This is so because, the society established schools to educate and prepare individuals who in turn will come back and solve societal problem. That is the more reason why whatever innovation is adopted must be reflective of the needs of the learners and that of the society. It is only when this is done that an act of innovation can be effective.

The underlying rationale of innovation simply put, is that, if the things of the present are not satisfying the needs of the present, workable strategies must be sought to ensure improved conditions, when this thinking is brought to bear on the curriculum innovation. (Izuagba, 2012). Innovation, may lead to modification or alteration of the previous conditions and practices. The consummation of the innovative conditions may however result in a change that may be total or partial depending on the magnitude of the innovation.

Izuagba (2012), came up with some reasons why curriculum innovations may be expedient, and they are;

- To cope with pressure and problems from social change, resulting from change that came into being due to pressure on our educational system due to the dynamism of our society.
- The need to utilize research findings geared towards teaching and learning.

- To explore opportunities with potentials for improved education.
- The need for improved teaching and learning.
- The need for education that is more relevant to the contemporary situation in the country.

It must be noted however that in adopting innovation, it should cut across all aspects of a curriculum. Therefore, innovation should originate from the aims and objectives, to the curriculum content, to the curriculum learning experiences, to the instructional methods and techniques, as well as in the evaluation strategies. Teachers and other personnel as well must be trained and retrained constantly so as to be able to keep in touch with the dictate of innovation, at all time.

For the purpose of these paper therefore, the Wheeler s model will serve as a promise for effective curriculum innovation.

Wheeler's Model

Wheeler develops the model in 1980 as a blue print for curriculum development, the model is also known as the cyclic, process or continuous model. These names came into being because of the circular representations of the five steps of the model. It must also be noted that the model came into existence in other to address the deficiencies in the Tyler's linear model, which was the first model. **The five steps are:**

1. Selection of aims, goals and objectives.
2. Selection of content (subject matter).
3. Selection of learning experiences.
4. Organisation and integration of content and learning experiences.
5. Evaluation (of all the stages of the curriculum developments, 1, 2, 3, 4 & 5) to ensure that the goals detailed in step 1 are attained.

Diagram of Wheeler's model

Wheeler (1980) Curriculum Process

The model shows the inter-relatedness of the five steps of the model in curriculum development. This shows that once the aims are determined, it is the aims that determines the content to be selected, because the content selected must lead to the achievement of aims, while the learning experiences selected must be related to the content, as well lead to the achievement of objectives. So also, the organization and integration of content and learning experiences must be done in such a way that they reinforce and support each other, in such a way that it must be related to the learning experiences and content, as well lead to the achievement of the aims and objectives. While the evaluation will now show the effectiveness of all the previous stages. The point to note here however, is that the results of evaluation will be fed back into the aims, goals and objectives in the form of innovation, and once that is done, all other stages 2, 3, 4 and 5 must be innovated upon. This is because all the stages or steps are dependent on the previous stage. Onyemerekeya (2001) was of the view that each phase is a logical development from the preceding one, and work in one stage cannot be attempted until work has been done in the preceding stage.

Making the Curriculum Functional

For a curriculum to be functional, it must be relevant to address the emergent needs and problems of both the learners as well the society. So, a curriculum is functional

only when it is solving the learner's problems as well as that of the society. This is why it is important just like in the Wheeler's model, that the curriculum must be constantly evaluated to determine whether it is still relevant to the need of the learners as well as to the need of the society. This is the reason why when there is a particular problem in the society to find solution to, there would always be an innovation in the curriculum towards the infusion of a particular subject in the school curriculum to address such a societal problem. Examples of such is the introduction into the school curriculum of subjects like agricultural science to tackle the problem of food shortage and unemployment in the country, computer science, so as not to be left behind as a country during the computer explosion, peace and conflict education to tackle the issue of insecurity and ethnic violence in the country.

All of these are attempts and efforts to make the curriculum functional by solving the learner's problems and solving societal problems. A country that is functional must reflect the needs and aspirations of learners and that of the society. That is why it is important that the curriculum should be constantly engaged to know whether it is performing these functions, engaging and making necessary changes at the level of aims, contents, learning experiences, organization and integration, as well at the evaluation level. This is why for the curriculum to be worthwhile and functional, the curriculum must be dynamic and must be constantly reviewed to reflect the emergent needs of the learners and the society.

A Functional Curriculum and Covid-19

The coronavirus is a family of viruses that ranges from the common cold, to severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS), and most recent of the virus is the one called covid-19, which was first detected in Wuhan, China in December of 2019. However, since the first reported case in China, covid-19 has spread to almost every country of the world. And as today, the 15th of April 2025, the number of recorded cases globally are: 761,402,282 confirmed cases of covid-19, including 6,887,000 deaths reported to WHO and a total of 13.3 billion vaccines have been administered. While, Nigeria has 266,660 confirmed cases of covid-19, 3,155 deaths and a total of 17,914,944 total vaccination.

The coronavirus pandemic came upon the world suddenly and brought the kind of devastation the world has never witnessed before to all sector and humanity, with death toll rising, schools were closed down all over the world to protect and contained the spread of the virus. However, most schools (kindergarten, primary, secondary and higher schools) were not prepared for this, and to respond to this therefore, schools, offices and other public spaces were closed down. The negative impact on education would most likely have been most devastating, because of the prolonged school closure. But for the swift response in the review of the school curriculum in a way for education to continue regardless of school closures, and so

many school systems were forced to turn to technology throughout the world as an alternative to normal school instruction which takes classes online.

This removes the teacher and the learner in space and distance in the name of virtual teaching and learning process, and so, school activities continued through a swift review of education curriculum towards the use of technology for every part of education. So, education continued, while other spaces (offices, and public spaces) were forced to remain closed. The use of technology through virtual teaching and learning, digital learning or e-learning, to deliver instruction to learners, which minimizes or eliminate totally, the need for teachers and learners to share classroom spaces. And so, even though the teacher and learners are not physically present with each other, teaching and learning is taking place. This is made possible because of a quick curriculum response which makes teaching and learning a virtual engagement with the use of computer software and internet to deliver instructions to learners. Virtual learning comes in different forms, which are:

- Computer based
- Internet based
- Remote teaching online
- Blended learning
- Facilitated virtual learning

It must be noted that, even though technology already had a big hand in most schools, the new dependence on technology for every aspect of education is such that was forced on us by the emergence of covid-19 and which curriculum has been able to respond to in solving both the learner's problems and societal problems.

Curriculum and Sustainable Development Goals

The term sustainable development has generated various definitions over the years. There has been an accepted definition of the concept before the Brundtland Report gave a definition to the concept in 1987. The United Nations also held a conference on Human Environment in 1972, and it was the conference that birthed the true understanding of sustainable development which resulted in the incorporation of social fairness and environmental caution into economic growth of nations and the establishment of United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) and United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). Thus, the definition of sustainable development by the Brundtland report became an operational explanation through which sustainable development is understood. This definition by Brundtland, became the lens through which sustainable development concept has been viewed by everyone across the globe. The definition espouses the idea that today's development and economic prosperity must not hamper the existence of the next generations of people who will live on the planet earth.

To justify the introduction of the SDGs, the United Nations General Assembly explained that the 17 Sustainable Development Goals and the 169 targets will demonstrate the scale and ambition of the new universal agenda. Through the sustainable development goals (SDGs), the United Nations hope to achieve the following lofty goals by the year 2030.

1. End poverty in all its form everywhere.
2. End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promotes sustainable agriculture.
3. Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all ages.
4. Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote life-long learning opportunities for all.
5. Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls
6. Ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation.
7. Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all.
8. Promote sustainable, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all.
9. Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation.
10. Reduce inequality within and among countries
11. Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable.
12. Ensure sustainable consumption and production.
13. Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts.
14. Conserve and sustainable use the oceans, seas and marines' resources for sustainable development.
15. Protect, restore, and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainable manage forests, combat desertification and halt reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss.
16. Promote peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development, provide access to justice for all and build effective, accountable and inclusive institutions at all levels.
17. Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize the global partnership for sustainable development. UNDP (2015).

However, despite the United Nations General Assembly emphasizing the place of economic and financial measures to ensure the successful implementation of the 2030 agenda, it has also reiterated the importance of using education through a functional curriculum as a tool to achieving these goals. It must therefore be noted that one unique and important framework to realise the sustainable development goals (SDGs) is education, through a functional curriculum. The United Nations General Assembly categorically stated that;

there is need to perfect the capacity of education structure
to get people ready to actively work at sustainable development
and to incorporate education for sustainable development

keenly into school curriculum further than the decade of education for sustainable development (UN General Assembly 2012:45)

To the Technical Support Team (TST), education through a functional curriculum is a cross-cutting issue for all the development goals. Maclean (2008) noted that even though, there are several alternative solutions to development, such as better infrastructure, such as better infrastructure, pipe-borne water, telecommunication amenities, good roads, telecommunication facilities, energy expansion etc. However, education through a functional curriculum remains and is still regarded as the main instrument for economic and social growth or development. He further explained that wherever education is properly delivered, it has been seen to engender: extreme poverty reduction; social equity and justice; social inclusion and orientation of the marginalised groups in the society and sustainable development. Arguing further that effective education helps to guarantee a safer, improved, more flourishing and ecologically secured world, while at the same time promoting socio-economic, cultural advancement, tolerance and international partnerships and corruption. In the same way, through a functional curriculum, education is seen as an instrument to raise people's income level and improve their standard of living.

Nevin (2008) explained that good and qualitative education through a functional curriculum is an important instrument for realising a more sustainable world. While Bokova (2014) assert that the Director General UNESCO in UNESCO publication titled; *shaping the future we want* (2014), explained that;

Education is the most potent tool to achieve sustainability.
Economic policies, technological inventions and interventions,
Political directives or fiscal incentives are not enough.
There is need for a fundamental change in the manner of
Peoples thinking and action (pg.16).

Education through effective teaching and learning is central to sustainable development. As explained by UNESCO (2005), through a functional curriculum, education and sustainable development are inseparable connected. In the submissions of Sterling (2014), the value of human life's and then environmental future is largely dependent on the cooperative capability to learn new things and facilitate change. UNESCO (2014) in the *Education for All Monitoring Global Monitoring Report (EFAGMR)* titled 'Sustainable Development begins with Education' indicated teaching and learning (education) can help in realising sustainable development in several areas which include reduction of poverty; improvement of nutrition; health benefit; equitable and inclusive education; gender balance and female empowerment confidence-building; clean water and sustainable electricity; economic advancement; reduction in social inequality; development of rural areas; protection and preservation of the ecology; peaceable, impartial and an inclusive communities. The report further concluded that teaching

and learning (education) through a functional curriculum can fast track advancement in the direction of achieving each of the anticipated sustainable development goals for 2015 and beyond in a variety of ways. The report maintained that not only is education a fundamental human right, but an essential instrument for social development and reconstruction. It further maintained that education empowers persons, particularly women, to live and seek for healthy, important, innovative and irrepressible lives.

It must be noted that, education for sustainable development cannot be fully achieved except sufficient and an undiluted attention is giving to the process of developing a functional curriculum that can be constantly reviewed (innovation) so as to accommodate the ability to achieving the 2030 sustainable development goals.

Conclusion

This paper highlights the various concept in education as they relate to sustainable development and the effect the emergence of the covid-19 pandemic is having on achieving the sustainable development goals. It is also clear from various discussions in the paper that the emergence of covid-19 might be a serious impediment towards achieving sustainable development goals (SDGs). It has also been established that even though we have 17 sustainable development goals (SDGs). Goal No.4, which is the 'provision of inclusive, equitable and quality education with lifelong learning opportunities for all' is the central point towards achieving all other goals. That is the reason why government across the globe are using education through innovations in school curriculum to respond to the effect of covid-19 pandemic. This to pave the way for the achievement of sustainable development goals (SDGs), with major focus on massive innovative infrastructural development to move in line according to the dictate of the spread of covid-19.

The sustainable development agenda of the United Nation has placed a huge responsibility on us of always developing an effective functional curriculum to achieve the 2030 development goals. It is therefore important that for us to move in this direction as a nation, our curriculum should accommodate the kind of teaching and learning that would be a pedagogical shift from the traditional implementation process of the curriculum to a 21st century teaching and learning, and also re-orientate teaching and learning that take a shift from education that emphasis on just passing school examination to a lifelong learning. We are in the 21st century where things happen faster than we can imagine, and to realise the objectives of education through a functional curriculum to achieving the sustainable development goals (SDGs). We must as a matter of urgency respond to the latest development in the field of education, where teaching and learning process is gradually shifting from the conventional face to face classroom interaction between the teacher and the learner to other mode of teaching and learning.

So, to be able to achieve the sustainable development goals (SDGs) speedily, there must be a development of an innovative functional curriculum that would take us totally away from the status quo in the educational system, where the emergence of covid-19 is trying to force on us as a nation. It is only when this is done that the aim of achieving the sustainable development goals (SDGs) in this period of covid-19 can be realistic.

Recommendations

It must be noted that education is fundamental to all human, economic, social and political development of any nation. Therefore, a comprehensive innovative and socially oriented curriculum is crucial for the nation's educational development. It is a known fact that the quality of education is low in the country due to (1). Insufficient fund, (2). Inadequate infrastructure, (3.) Lack of material resources (4.) Lack of human resources and many more, largely contribute to this, and as a result, if there is an index employed to measure education performance in the country, Nigeria will score low. So, to be able to achieve the sustainable development goals (SDGs) in this covid-19 era, there must be such innovations in the curriculum that should emphasis

- Competency-based learning
- Open curriculum
- Digital textbook
- Virtual and augmented reality.

An effort to develop extensive research on key innovative issues must also be embarked upon so as to enhance the knowledge of educators on innovative methods of teaching that would help the achievement of the sustainable development goals (SDGs) through an innovative curriculum.

Functional curriculum that can be easily reviewed should be developed, so as to enable educators gain insights about new values, mindsets, competences, and skills needed to realised the SDGs agenda of 2930 because of the new normal that the covid-19 has forced on us.

There should also be an expanded awareness of the exchanges needed at the individual, organisational, and institutional levels to effectively change mindsets. Curriculum developed should be tailored towards the achievement of SDGs during the period of covid-19 pandemic.

Innovative, dynamic curriculum that find its way around covid-19 should be developed across all levels of education in the country and genuine efforts should be made for learners to acquire practical hands-on knowledge and skills on how to trigger change at different levels (individuals, organisational and governmental).

A road-map and an action plan should be developed to apply relevant knowledge and skills on educational delivery through digital devices which should be made available in schools and affordable for individual learners.

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